

History of War "The Battles of Palagan Ambarawa" Reviewed From Universal War Strategy Perspective

Tonny Sumarno¹, I Wayan Midhio², Deni D.A.R³, Rizerius Eko⁴
Lukman Yudho Prakoso⁵

Indonesia Defence University, Sentul, Bogor, Indonesia

Abstract: The first President of the Republic of Indonesia, Ir. Soekarno, once advised the Indonesian people, "Never Forget The History (Red Coat)". This message certainly has a deep meaning so that the Indonesian nation will respect and honor its heroes who died and sacrificed in gaining independence from colonialism. Studying history is important for the nation's future generations, so that they love their homeland, are proud and have a high sense of nationalism. The lack of literature on the history of the nation's struggle is one of the obstacles for researchers and academics in exploring more deeply the heroic stories of heroes that can be used as lessons in filling independence. Scientifically, the history of the nation's struggle must be explained based on the rules of ontology, epistemology and axiology, so that the study of a history can be scientifically justified. The purpose of this research is to analyze the implementation of the implementation of the universal war strategy at the time of the "Battle of Palagan Ambarawa", and how the government's efforts to increase the love of the homeland of the young generation of the nation in filling independence, as well as meeting the limitations of literature on the history of the nation's struggle. The method used in this study uses historical methodology by carrying out four stages of activities, namely, Heuristic, Criticism, Interpretation and Presentation of the synthesis in the form of a story. From the results of research and historical tracing based on secondary data sources, it was found that the "Battle of Palagan Ambarawa" had implemented a universal war strategy, so it could be concluded that the elements of democracy, universality and territory in the implementation of the universal war strategy could defend the country's sovereignty. and in order to increase the sense of nationalism and love for the homeland, the young generation of the nation must be given the "Defend the Nation" program, while the constraints on the limitations of literature on the history of the nation's struggle must be met by the government by reproducing historical reading in the world of education through libraries. So that efforts to develop knowledge, historical studies from various aspects of research can fulfill the rules of ontology, epistemology and axiology of science.

Keywords:History of War, The Battle,sovereignty,Palagan Ambarawa, Universal War, Strategy

I. Introduction

War, according to the Great Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI), has the meaning of hostility between two countries, then both parties mobilize their military strength to fight using their weapons (Kemdikbud, 2019) but war also has various meanings, so in essence the meaning of war itself can be interpreted as a form of all the efforts of a country in exerting all its capabilities to fight for its goals in defending the sovereignty of its country,

¹Indonesian Defense University student, Universal War Strategy Study Program, Sentul, Bogor, Indonesia

²Indonesian Defense University Lecturer, Sentul, Bogor, Indonesia/ iwayan.midhio@idu.ac.id

³Indonesian Defense University Lecturer, Sentul, Bogor, Indonesia/ denidar@idu.ac.id

⁴Indonesian Defense University Lecturer, Sentul, Bogor, Indonesia/ rizerius87@gmail.com

⁵Indonesian Defense University Lecturer, Sentul, Bogor, Indonesia/lukman.prakoso@idu.ac.id

and not only relying on the capabilities of its armed forces. The essence of that understanding is then interpreted as Universal War, which is a form of war strategy used by the Indonesian nation in facing all kinds of threats that want to disturb the nation's sovereignty. This universality is then realized through the mobilization of all Indonesian national strength and resources to face threats from within the country and from abroad (Prabowo, 2019).

Discussing war is of course closely related to the word defense, whereas defense itself has a very broad meaning. Defense is the study of how to manage national resources and strength in times of peace, war and after the war, in order to face external and domestic threats, both in the form of military and non-military threats to territorial integrity, state sovereignty and safety. The entire nation in order to realize national security (Supriyanto, 2014). With the rapid development of science and technology at this time, strategies and equipment for war infrastructure continue to develop, however, all these developments are inseparable from a series of war history that has occurred before. The history of war during World War I and II has illustrated to all of us that war brings more suffering. The damage to infrastructure, the number of casualties and the destruction of the system of a government, and of course, are very valuable lessons for all of us.

Studying history and defense in fighting in a philosophical manner is very important, especially in analyzing past and present war incidents, in terms of the strategic and tactical aspects used at that time, to be used as evaluation and benchmarks and finding the relevance of a strategy which can be used as a basis for the future, of course the transformation of the strategies and tactics studied has been adjusted to the current dynamic conditions. In philosophy, strategy or war is an analysis of knowledge or "Science" which ontology seeks to know or study war itself, then epistemologically tries to find out how to get this knowledge and axiologically, what will this knowledge be used for?

The Battle of Palagan Ambarawa was one of the battles of the "Eight Palagan" who fought in seizing and defending Indonesia's independence. Eight Palagan who greatly determined the fate of the Indonesian nation after the Proclamation of Independence of the Republic of Indonesia on August 17, 1945, namely: Palagan Medan, Palagan Palembang, Palagan Bandung, Palagan Semarang, Palagan Surabaya, Palagan Makasar, Palagan Margarana and Palagan Ambarawa (Disjarah AD, 2014). On October 20, 1945, allied troops under the leadership of Brigadier Bethell landed in Semarang with the intention of taking care of Japanese prisoners of war and soldiers who were in Central Java. The arrival of these allies was accompanied by NICA (Netherlands Indies Civil Administration). At first, the arrival of the allies was welcomed by the Indonesian people, even the governor of Central Java, Mr Wongsonegoro, agreed to provide food and other necessities for the smooth running of the allies' duties as long as the allies promised not to interfere with the sovereignty of the Republic of Indonesia. However, when the allied forces and NICA arrived in Ambarawa and Magelang to free the prisoners of the Dutch army, the prisoners were actually armed, causing anger from the Indonesian side (Muqtadiroh&Kuswardayan, 2012). Japan's failure to maintain the status quo in the Dutch East Indies (Indonesia) was one of the reasons the Allies failed to accept the handover of power over Indonesia to the Allies by Japan. The allies' efforts to restore Dutch rule (NICA) in Indonesia were the root of the problem and the cause of the fighting in Ambarawa.

From the background described above, the researcher is interested in analyzing the history of war from the story of the Battle of Palagan Ambarawa on November 20 to December 15, 1945, with the formulation of the problem, "How is the Battle of Palagan Ambarawa viewed from the Perspective of Universal War Strategy"? By analyzing the historical events of this "Palagan Ambarawa Battle", it is hoped that it will be able to foster a fighting spirit and love for the country for all the nation's children and find the relevance of the use of past and present tactics and strategies from the perspective of the Universal War Strategy.

II. Method

The research methodology used by researchers in analyzing the problems to be studied is using historical research methodologies. In historical methodology, a historian is required to master the methods used to find out past events. For this reason, a study was conducted in the form of an investigative procedure using historical data collection techniques, both in the form of archives and libraries at home and abroad, as well as

interviews with figures who lived and were involved in these historical events. Historical research is one of the studies classified as "historical method", namely a research method specifically used in historical research through certain stages. The application of the historical method takes work stages, as stated by Noto Susanto (1971: 17) in Sulasman (2014: 75), namely:

- a. Heuristic, namely by collecting traces of the past;
- b. Criticism (history), namely investigating whether the trace is true, both in form and in content;
- c. Interpretation, namely determining the meaning and interrelation of the facts obtained by history; and
- d. Presentation, namely conveying the synthesis obtained in the form of a story.

Thus, the historical method is an implementation guide and technical guidance regarding the material, criticism, interpretation and presentation of history. In research using the historical method, various types of historical writing are described, units of study, problems, theories, concepts and historical sources.

III. Results and Discussion

3.1 History of the Battle of Palagan Ambarawa (Heuristic)

Etymologically, the word history comes from Arabic, namely *syajarah*, which means tree of life, roots, descent and origin. It is so named because the initial focus of the discussion of history in the classical period was tracing the origin and genealogy (line: descent), which is generally described as "a tree of descent or family)", whereas in English, history is called history which is defined as "the development of everything in time "or the development of everything in a time. Judging from this explanation, we can understand that talking about historical problems cannot be separated from stories about events and incidents in the dimensions of time or time that have passed which are arranged chronologically, so that it can be concluded that history is a story of changes, events or past events which have been given interpretations or reasons and linked so as to provide a complete understanding. Since the 13th century, in line with the development of modern technology, history has had a special position and meaning as a branch of science (Kuntowijoyo, 1995: 1-2) in Sulasman (2014: 17).

The Battle of Palagan Ambarawa was one of the battles of the "Eight Palagan" who fought in order to defend the Independence of the Republic of Indonesia from the Allied efforts to piggyback on NICA to return to colonize Indonesia. The Allied presence in Ambarawa threatened Central Java and Yogyakarta, so the People's Security Army (TKR) troops made plans to attack the Allies in Ambarawa. In Indonesian historiography, the incident of "Battle of Palagan Ambarawa" is one of the national historical events, however the scarcity of information sources about this event is one of the reasons for the scarcity of research on the history of "Battle of Palagan Ambarawa" in Indonesia, the centralization of power, especially during the "Orde Baru" era. has neglected the region as a source of value and identity, causing history in the region to be neglected too. By examining historical events at the local level, of course in the future it will be able to help the scarcity of information about history in coloring the entire historical context of the wider revolution.

3.2 The Battle of Palagan Ambarawa and Indonesian Historiography (Criticism)

Very few literatures that raise historical events related to the story of the Ambarawa battle have been explained very little, but over time, writings or research on history slowly but surely began to be in great demand. The rapid development of science and technology and the advancement of the world of education have led to significant changes. The Battle of Palagan Ambarawa and several heroic events in it, have so far been kept neatly in the Army History Service. The writings about the Battle of Palagan Ambarawa during the post-war independence revolution, historiographically, Indonesian national history and local historiography have not been widely studied, this is due to the lack of information sources and sources that can contribute maximally in its compilation. If we look for literary sources that discuss the Ambarawa battle at the Gramedia bookstore or online bookstore, there are only Palagan Ambarawa fighting books published by the Army History Service.

There have been several papers that have tried to raise the story of Ambarawa's battle, including a thesis by Nur Laela, a student at the State Islamic University of Sunan Kalijaga Yogyakarta with the title

"Parakan-Temanggung People's Struggle in Maintaining the Independence of the Republic of Indonesia", then an article from Lutfi et al. Students of the History Education Study Program. , FKIP UNS Surakarta, with the title of the article raised about "Museum Isdiman Palagan Ambarawa as a Source and Media for Learning History of SMA Negeri 1 Ambarawa". Other articles that tell about the Ambarawa battle are also found on many websites on the internet but cannot be used as a solid basis as a research source. The lack of data sources in uncovering the history of the story of the Palagan Ambarawa battle has led to the lack of writings and research on history in this country, and of course there are many more stories of regional struggle that have yet to be revealed.

3.3 Historical Explanation in the Battle of Palagan Ambarawa (Interpretation)

The explanatory model used in analyzing the Battle of Palagan Ambarawa during this revolutionary period is social history with a realist epistemology which is a continuation development as well as a middle way between post modernism and structurism in historical science. According to a sociological perspective, the Ambarawa people's resistance to the Allies can be said to be a social action, according to Llyod (1993: 95) in Sulasman (2014: 329) that the actions of the Ambarawa people in the battle of the Ambarawapalagan are categorized into collective action. Meanwhile, according to Tilly (1978: 7) in Salasman (2014: 329) is the effort of people who act together to achieve common interests. This then provides the direction for the action to be carried out. Collective Action has 5 (five) action components, namely common interest, organization, mobilization, opportunity and collective action. For the Battle of the Battle of Ambarawa, the collective action used is the mobilization model analysis.

In the collective action model the mobilization of this process starts from the existence of common interests and then takes action, this process can be carried out in 4 (four) ways: First, it is encouraged by mutual interests then forming an organization, mobilizing and finally taking action. Second, there is a common interest which then encourages further mobilization to take action. Third, common interests encourage to assess the interests of other groups. If the interest of the group is in a favorable position, it means that the group has the opportunity (opportunity), but if other groups are stronger then this group will be threatened (Threat). If threats are no longer a problem then proceed with taking action, or mobilizing first and then continuing with action. Fourth, in relation to other social groups, the interests of these groups can be suppressed (repression) or even supported (facilitation) then proceed with mobilization and actions or actions (Salasman, 2014)

Source: History Metodology book, P. 229

3.4 Causal Factors "The Battle of Palagan Ambarawa" (Historiography)

Starting from the Japanese ambition which was obsessed with dominating Asia by launching an invasion in the Greater East Asian war and the United States' efforts to prevent a Japanese invasion because of the United States' concern that if Japan came to power in Asia it would interfere with the interests of the United

States (PK Ojong, 2009). -2 in the Pacific is inevitable. When Japan first landed in Indonesia and succeeded in conquering the Dutch, the situation in Java, especially Ambarawa, underwent many changes. The Dutch who were originally in power in Indonesia were then thrown into detention (internment camp) in Ambarawa, and because of the large number of Dutch prisoners, the Dutch barriers were changed to internment camps (Disjarah, 1979). Thus, since 1942 Indonesia was officially under Japanese rule. At the beginning of the Japanese occupation of Indonesia, Japan was in a state of urgency to face the attacks of the United States and the Allies. In Indonesia, Japan then tried to find natural resources, oil and other logistical materials that could be used to support the Greater East Asian war. The Japanese efforts did not stop there, Colonel Fujiyama, one of the Japanese military leaders at the time, came to see Soekarno and tried to persuade Soekarno to help the Greater East Asian war Japan, Japan said that the war he was doing was Japan's attempt to free Asia from colonialism and the suppression of western colonialism (Cindy Adams, 2014).

At the time of the Japanese occupation, Bung Karno's political role greatly determined the historical direction of the Indonesian struggle. Japan tried to take advantage of the people's love for Bung Karno in order to support all the needs of Japan in Indonesia, while Bung Karno tried to take advantage of Japan with the promise of independence. The dynamics at the time of the Japanese occupation were very complex. Japanese actions against the Indonesian people were arbitrary and the desire to liberate the Indonesian nation was raging in Bung Karno's chest. Since then, the Indonesian people were mobilized by Japan, Japan awakened the Indonesian people who slept long, the Indonesian people were mobilized by being taught various kinds of social activities, saving, cleaning the environment and organizing and on the other hand, Indonesian youths were mobilized in the military, who are members of (PETA, Heiho, Seinendai, Keibodan, Fujinkai, Jawa Hokokai and Jibakutai) to face the Allied attacks (Wiretno, 2017)

The Allied retaliation attack in World War II against Japanese military power, day by day progressed very rapidly, until the peak of the Allies dropped atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki on August 6 and 9 1945. So that on August 15, 1945 Japan surrendered unconditional to the Allies. Two months before World War II ended, to be precise in July 1945, the Joint Chiefs of Staff of the Allied Forces held a conference at Potsdam, based on the Potsdam conference, Indonesian landings and occupations were handed over to British troops who were members of SEAC (South East Asia Command). , led by Vice Admiral Lord Louis Mounthbatten. Given the vast area that is the responsibility of SEAC, specifically for Indonesia a special task force was formed, namely the Allied Force Netherland East Indies (AFNEI), (Disjarah AD, 2014)

The British military force deployed in the AFNEI unit consists of three divisions under the command of Lieutenant General Christison, the unit consists of the 23rd Indian Division under the leadership of General DC Hawthorn, the V Division under the leadership of Major General EG Manserg and the 26th Indian Division under the leadership Major General HM Chambers. The Allied troops who landed in Indonesia had a mission to disarm the Japanese army which numbered around 60,000 personnel and free RAPWI (Release Allied Prisoners of War and Interness) prisoners. However, covertly carrying out the main task of restoring Dutch sovereignty from the colonies of the Dutch East Indies (Indonesia), as stated in the Civil Affairs Agreement that was signed between the British and Dutch governments. Based on the agreement, Britain fully recognized Dutch sovereignty over Indonesia, so that the British and the Allies did not question this. Japan's failure to maintain the "status quo" in Indonesia until the arrival of the Allies was considered a failure because the Indonesian nation had proclaimed its independence. Japan was helpless because the Indonesian nation at that time was really ready to be independent whatever happened later, the Japanese people were also worried about the wrath of the youths who joined the military formed by Japan. In carrying out international duties, the Allies committed many violations, apart from arming the released Dutch prisoners with Japanese weapons, the Allies also violated the agreement to involve Indonesian soldiers in the process of repatriating prisoners of war. The Allied efforts to piggyback on NICA (Netherlands Indies Civil Administration) in restoring Dutch rule in Indonesia was one of the causes of the fighting in the "Eight Palagan" in Indonesia, one of which was the Battle of Palagan Ambarawa.

In addition to the political problems above, the "causal factor" of the Battle of Palagan Ambarawa is an economic problem, where Ambarawa is a fertile area that has very large plantations, Ambarawa's geographical conditions make it very possible for the development of agricultural land, the air is cool and various kinds of plantation crops can flourish. such as cloves, tea, coffee, nutmeg and chocolate and there are rivers running as power plants. Its strategic location made the Dutch colonial government see it was important to build its military strength and establish fortifications, barriers and increase the strength of its personnel. Economically, Ambarawa is very profitable because it is rich in natural resources, besides that by controlling Ambarawa, it will be easier for the Dutch to attack the Indonesian Army Headquarters in Yogyakarta from Ambarawa.

3.3.1 Battle Locations

Learning from the failure to control the Magelang region, when they arrived in Ambarawa, the Allied troops no longer used Dutch troops to attack the People's Security Army (TKR), but instead used Japanese troops who previously controlled Ambarawa in 1942-1945. The Allied Forces realized that the Japanese troops really controlled the Ambarawa area and knew the weaknesses of the TKR troops (Disjarahad, 1979). This was due to an emotional connection because they had trained TKR troops from PETA, Heiho and Kaigun. The status of Japanese troops as prisoners of war was actually used by the Allies to attack TKR troops. The Allied strategy turned out to be beneficial for the Allies, the TKR troops were successfully beaten back from Temanggung, Ambarawa. After causing various chaos and battles, the Allies managed to set up defenses at Ambarawa. Meanwhile, in the city center, the TKR troops and fighting agencies and Laskar fought back, by boycotting Allied foodstuffs, and cutting off the link between Semarang - Magelang, and Semarang - Ambarawa. Which in the end forced the allied forces to have a meeting with the Indonesian republic government. The Allied demand was rejected and the Allies strengthened their stronghold by placing Howitzer Cannons around Ambarawa Square.

Apart from the blockade of foodstuffs and road blockades, the Ambarawa youth also blocked tap water to the Allied Headquarters, they raided the Allied rice and food warehouses, taking boxes of Allied Logistics. The youth guarded the water sources to prevent the Allied troops from fetching water from the water sources. The waterways were all blocked resulting in the Allies being short of water. To solve this problem, the Allies contacted the Ambarawa youth by sending an envoy escorted by Gurkha troops to ask about the water problem. The TKR commander in Patoman Ambarawa village gave a signal to Ambarawa residents and youths, when he heard three gunshots, it meant that the Indonesian people would be involved in fighting with the Allies in Ambarawa, the residents who did not participate in the battle to immediately evacuate (Disjarah, 1970)

3.3.2 Mobilization

Mobilization is the act of simultaneously mobilizing and utilizing national resources and national facilities and infrastructure that have been fostered and prepared as components of the state defense and security forces to be used appropriately, integratedly and with direction for overcoming any threat, both from abroad and from within the country. RI Law Number 27, 1997) Whereas in Law Number 23 of 2019, it is explained that Mobilization is imposed on reserve components, and supporting components subject to mobilization must have their status upgraded as reserve components (RI Law Number 23, 2019). Where this is related to their rights and obligations in defending the country.

In the mobilization process at the Battle of Palagan Ambarawa, the People's Security Army (TKR) worked together with the people to fight against the Allies in order to defend the Independence of the Republic of Indonesia. The organization used in the collective action of the Battle of Palagan Ambarawa is the army in collaboration with the people who are members of the people's classes. Seeing the great strength of Indonesian youth, especially those who have received military education from Japan, KNIL and other semi-military organizations, the TKR Chief of General Staff (KSU) formed four divisions, one in Sumatra and three in Java Island, the number of youths who volunteered to join in TKR exceeded the planned amount. So that originally four divisions became 10 divisions which were divided into 35 regiments. Other fighting agencies involved include, Hizbullah, Laskar Rakyat, KRIS, PIM, Pesindo, BPRI, AMRI, TRM, Bald Forces and others.

To strengthen in the field of weaponry, it was obtained from the spoils of the Japanese army either without resistance or with resistance, so that there was a battle first. The number of weapons that could be seized from the Japanese army included: 5000 rifles, 700 pistols, 500 steins or PMs, 150 SMRs, 2 7.5 field guns, 2 7.5 mountain cannons, 5 beach cannons and 4 bullet sheds, 1 Zeni warehouse and 1 transportation equipment (communication), 13 sedans, 60 trucks, 4 bren carriers and others which are estimated to be sufficient for the war needs of one Brigade within 3 years.

Strategy and Tactics

Carl von Clausewitz in his theory states that strategy is the art of using battle to win warfare, Clausewitz also defines that strategy is:

"The employment of the battle as the means towards the attainment of the object of the war"

Strategy is the use of combat as a means of obtaining war objectives, devising ways of fighting to achieve objectives. There are three moral forces that Clausewitz considered very important in developing strategy and warfare. First is the ability of the war commander, second, the military values of the troops and third is the feeling of nationalism from all elements, and one of the other important moral forces is the boldness or fearlessness, this fear should not come into action. opposing orders or disobedience to leaders (Marsono&Legionosuko, 2020)

After being elected as Commander of the People's Security Army (TKR). The TKR Commander gave his mandate, "The army has only one authority, it is to defend the sovereignty of the State and maintain its safety, discipline must be adhered to, submit to the leadership of its superiors, sincerely carry out its duties. It must also be remembered that it is not enough for the Indonesian State to be defended by the army, so it is necessary to establish close cooperation with groups and agencies outside the army. The army should not be the tool of any group or person"(Disjarahad, 1978). Therefore the General Concept of TKR resistance operations under Colonel Sudirman's leadership was to balance the superiority of Allied weaponry, namely, by carrying out sporadic battles in various cities in Central Java as well as in various places in Ambarawa, through sabotage, logistical blockades, water and electricity and other obstructive actions. Especially for the battle in Ambarawa, the Army Headquarters (TKR) prepared four TKR divisions in Central Java to face battles against Allied troops, NICA and Japan in the Bethell Brigade in Ambarawa.

In the first stage, the Battle Leadership Headquarters (MPP) under the leadership of Colonel Sudirman prepared an operational plan based on intelligence reports, then divided the battlefield in Ambarawa into 3 sectors, namely: South Sector, West Sector and East Sector. In this stage the attack was directed at suppressing the position of the British army in Magelang, after successfully suppressing the British position in Magelang, the next stage of the attack on Ambarawa was divided into four sectors, namely: South, West, North and East Sector. Before taking part in the Ambarawa battle, many TKR troops, members of the armed struggle and the People's Army purified themselves, seeking invulnerability, amulets for bullet protection and carrying magical and unseen fortune. Among them are the sharpened bamboo sticks that have been spelled out by Kyai Subkhi and other kyai. The appearance of these scholars gave extraordinary enthusiasm for the fighters in facing the Allies, NICA and Japan in the Battle of Palagan Ambarawa.

Siege of the Allies in Ambarawa is planned to be carried out from all sectors that are bound for Ambarawa. Then on the evening of December 11, 1945, at the carik house of the Ambarawa sub-district, Colonel Sudirman gathered the Battle Sector Commanders and the People's Army Class Commanders to gather and consolidate the Allied attack plan in Ambarawa. After getting the advice and input from the Sector Commanders, it was decided that the strategy to be used in the release of Ambarawa would be carried out with fast, simultaneous attacks from all sectors and at the same time, the attack command would be held by the TKR sector commanders, the attack started tomorrow morning. Pk. 04.30 right. During the consolidation, siege tactics and strategies were described by the name of the tactic "Supit Urang" (Jarahdam VII Diponegoro, 1979).

3.3.4 The Course of Battle

The attack was initiated by first controlling the main road axis between Ambarawa-Semarang, because by controlling the Ambarawa-Semarang highway route, it would make it easier to encircle the Allied forces inside the city of Ambarawa. Squeeze the enemy tightly from all directions so that the allies only have the opportunity to escape from one direction, namely the Ambarawa Semarang road. After the consolidation meeting is over, the time matching is carried out by matching the hours of each sector commander. Towards the hour "J" all sectors prepare for the position of the troops including the attacking troops to be deployed. The siege tactic known as the "Supit Urang" tactic was well received by the Sector Commanders. In the application of the supiturang tactic, it is a movement of attacking forces from the south and west to the east towards Semarang. In his efforts to destroy the Allies, Colonel Sudirman really applied the principles of war science as an operational basis, such as the principle of objective, the principle of offensive, the principle of unity of command, the principle of concentration, the principle of surprise, the principle of moral excellence, and the most important principle was the principle of never giving up. . In this battle Colonel Sudirman coordinated TKR troops from various regions, such as: TKR Magelang, Yogyakarta, Purwokerto, Semarang, Solo, Salatiga and several other areas in a shrimp configuration. Where the right supit is in the position of the guava area, the left supit is in the tail area which is supported by the tail or reserve troops in Sumowono.

In the Battle of Palagan Ambarawa, the TKR troops who carried out siege against the enemy position could only drive the Allies from Ambarawa but could not destroy them. The number of TKR troops surrounding Ambarawa was indeed much larger than the Allied troops (British) so that within one and a half hours from the start of the attack, TKR troops had succeeded in besieging Ambarawa and pinning the enemy from various directions in the Ambarawa area of operation. For four days and four nights fighting took place in Ambarawa. The Allied Forces, NICA, and Japan were increasingly under pressure, and at the peak of the TKR troops penetrating the Allied center at Fort Willem I, the remaining Allied forces attempted to break through the defenses of the TKR troops and leave Ambarawa, fleeing to the city of Semarang. The Battle of Palagan Ambarawa became a heroic event and became an important event in the history of the Indonesian resistance during the physical revolution.

3.3.5 “The Battle of the Palagan Ambarawa”Reviewed from a Universal War Strategy Perspective

As explained in the description in the introduction, the Universal War Strategy is a form of war strategy used by the Indonesian nation in facing all kinds of threats that want to disturb the nation's sovereignty. This universality is then realized through the mobilization of all Indonesian national strength and resources to face threats from within the country and from abroad. The essence of the universal war strategy itself is a total war for all Indonesian people by mobilizing all national strength and resources to uphold state sovereignty, territorial integrity and national safety from other nations that threaten or occupy the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI). The People's War of the Universe has a populist, universal and territorial nature, where the social aspect is manifested through the participation of all Indonesian people in accordance with their roles, abilities, professions and expertise as a manifestation of their rights and obligations in defending the country. The universality is realized through the mobilization of all Indonesian national strength and resources to be mobilized in the interests of facing threats, both from outside and from within the country, while territoriality is manifested in the form of the involvement of the entire territory of the country as a fighting space in developing a defense strategy in order to achieve the objectives of the strategy. war of the universe.

The Battle of Palagan Ambarawa which was held on 12 to 15 December 1945, under the command of Panglima Sudirman, had essentially implemented elements in the Universal War Strategy, using tactics of griliary warfare, popular support and the use of national assets and resources in carrying out battles and mobilization in achieving war objectives with the principles of war which made the guidelines for its implementation able to drive the Allied troops (British), NICA and Japan out of the city of Ambarawa. The use of griliary tactics and sporadic warfare with a strategy of support supported by Colonel Sudirman's leadership qualities was able to provide influence, enthusiasm and high mental mentality and support from all components of the nation armed only with spoiled weapons, ammunition and Japanese war equipment. Colonel Sudirman as Commander of Division V was able to organize the task and command organization properly. The role of intelligence in supporting data and information for the preparation of an operational plan is very helpful in its implementation. The elements in implementing the main strategy, namely: Ends, Means and Ways in the application of the Universal War Strategy with the tactics of "Supit Urang" compiled by Colonel Sudirman, can be described as follows:

- a. **Ends:** Ends or the goal to be achieved at the Battle of Palagan Ambarawa was to drive Allied troops (British, NICA and Japanese out of Ambarawa city, so that the Allied mission to dominate Central Java by strengthening their defenses in Ambarawa could be thwarted.
- b. **Means:** In supporting the Battle of Palagan Ambarawa, Colonel Sudirman as the control and command of the battle, took advantage of the facilities and infrastructure of weapons, bullets and vehicle assets from the Japanese army as well as traditional weapons (bamboo spikes), mobilizing the People's Class, youth and military organizations. during the Japanese occupation (PETA, Heiho, KNIL (Netherlands), kyai and santri to jointly struggle to defend the independence of the Republic of Indonesia.
- c. **Ways :** In the "Battle of Palagan Ambarawa", Colonel Sudirman carried out sporadic warfare to reduce enemy strength, sabotaged airfields, main roads and cut off enemy logistics, including sabotaging the flow of water, blocking and seizing the weapons of the Allied Forces, NICA and Japan, then Colonel Sudirman divided troops into four sectors (South, North, East and West) to pinch and surround the enemy with the "Supit Urang" strategy, then destroy the enemy with sudden and simultaneous attacks from four directions at 04.30, so as to repel the enemy (Allies, NICA, and Japan) out of the city of Ambarawa.

The Battle of Palagan Ambarawa, which was carried out by Colonel Sudirman and his troops, in an effort to drive the Allied troops out of the city of Ambarawa, had basically implemented elements of the Universal War Strategy, namely: Population, Universality and Territoriality. When faced with the dynamics of the current strategic environment, the implementation of the Universal War Strategy will continue to develop dynamically. The rapid advancement of science, technology, information and communication and globalization will create a different paradigm. However, with the historical background and cultural culture of the Indonesian people as well as Indonesia's geographic location, the implementation of the Universal War Strategy is still relevant and worthy of being defended.

IV. Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1 Conclusion

- a. The implementation of the Universal War Strategy at the Battle of Palagan Ambarawa on 12-15 December 1945 was well applied by Colonel Sudirman and the TKR troops supported by the fighters and the people in Central Java. The strategy and tactics of the Universal War were carried out by involving the people, facilities and infrastructure from the existing national resources and regional throughout Central Java, the tactics and strategies of giliary warfare with sporadic attacks by implementing defense pockets by involving the people to fight together. must continue to be developed and transformed in accordance with the dynamics of the times it is facing at this time.
- b. Studying the history of the Indonesian nation's war in seizing and defending Independence is very important, which can be passed on to the nation's future younger generations. the values of struggle, love for the homeland and pride as an Indonesian nation must continue to be well imprinted, especially in filling independence with positive things without forgetting the history of struggle of their ancestors.
- c. The lack of data sources in finding references as research material and study of war history has become an obstacle in the preparation of writing that discusses the study of combat strategies and tactics, especially in case studies of wars that have been carried out by the Indonesian nation. The study of strategy and tactics in combat must be scientifically explained both in ontology, epistemology, and axiology. So that the study of the relevance of using tactics and strategies can be accounted for academically.

4.2 Recommendations

a. Judging from historical experience in fighting and the use of tactics and strategies in dealing with the enemy, the tactics of grile war used by Colonel Sudirman and his troops by creating pockets of defense, the involvement of the people and the use of existing national resource assets with the involvement of all regions in supporting the battle, so that need to be analyzed and studied in the face of current conditions, both in terms of ontology, epistemology and scientific axiology, in order to obtain accountable scientific studies, the government needs to support these research activities, especially in the face of the development plan of the "Big Islands Defense strategy" planned by The current Ministry of Defense.

b. In order to pass on the values of the struggle of the ancestors who have liberated the Indonesian nation from colonialism, as well as increasing love for the homeland and being proud of being the Indonesian nation, the Government should pay attention to the needs of the current generation of young generations of the nation, by providing state defense programs in the education curriculum. in Indonesia. This state defense program can also be given to all institutional sectors in government and the private sector.

c. Lack of reading material related to history, especially literature on the "Battle of the Palagan Ambarawa". In order for the local government of Ambarawa district to increase readings or literature on the history of the nation's struggle, especially those related to the Battle of the Ambarawa Palace in each library, it is hoped that it will increase a sense of nationalism and pride as an Indonesian nation

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